

POSSIBLE ANTIAMOEBIIC AGENTS. PART VII.
ANALOGUES OF CAMOFORM

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Several Mannich base hydrochlorides have been synthesised from substituted allylphenols with a view to testing them for their antiamebic activity.

Recently Park Davis & Co. has introduced camoform as an effective amoebicide. It was first synthesised as a possible antimalarial by Burckhalter *et al.* (*J. Amer. Chem. Soc.*, 1946, 68, 1894). Clinical trials by Hoekenga *et al.* (*Am. J. Trop. Med. & Hyg.*, 1954, 3, 849) revealed it to be a non-toxic amoebicide, the cure rate being as high as 85%. Structurally, camoform is the dihydrochloride (I) of the Mannich base, derived from 4:4'-dihydroxy-3:3'-diallyldiphenyl. In the present investigation a number of Mannich base hydrochlorides (II), analogous to camoform, have been synthesised from unsaturated phenols, containing an allyl or propenyl grouping and another substituent (chloro, methyl, *tert.*-butyl or methoxy) with a view to studying the effect of simplifying the camoform molecule in relation to its antiamebic activity.

[R_1 & R_2 = substituents in the nucleus ;
 R' & R'' = substituents in the basic side chain].

The allylphenols were prepared by the Claisen rearrangement of the corresponding allyl phenyl ethers.

Mannich base hydrochlorides have been prepared from eugenol (*o*-methoxy-*p*-allylphenol), *o*-allyl-*p*-methyl-, *o*-allyl-*p*-chloro- and *o*-allyl-*p*-*tert.*-butyl-phenols, using formaldehyde and different amines, viz., benzylamine, morpholine, piperidine and piperazine, following the method of Bruson *et al.* (*J. Amer. Chem. Soc.*, 1941, 63, 270).

TABLE I
 Mannich base hydrochloride

Sl. No.	R ₁ & R ₂	R' & R''	M.P.	% Yield	Formula.	% Nitrogen		M.P.	Formula.	% Nitrogen	
						Found.	Calc.			Found.	Calc.
1.	2-Methoxy-4-allyl-	Benzyl-	167-68°	74	C ₁₈ H ₂₁ O ₂ NCl	4.20	4.38	...	...	...	...
2.	"	Morpholinyl-	183°	95	C ₁₅ H ₂₁ O ₂ NCl	4.72	4.67	134°	C ₂₁ H ₂₉ O ₁₀ N ₄	11.20	11.38
3.	"	Piperidyl-	157°	82	C ₁₆ H ₂₄ O ₂ NCl	4.60	4.71	148°	C ₂₇ H ₃₆ O ₈ N ₄	11.30	11.43
4a*	"	Piperazine	145°	64	C ₂₈ H ₃₄ O ₂ N ₂	6.26	6.39	...	...	...	...
4b	"	"	220°	...	C ₂₈ H ₃₈ O ₄ N ₂ Cl ₂	5.58	5.48	...	...	...	...
5.	2-Allyl-4-methyl-	Benzyl-	132°	91	C ₁₈ H ₂₇ ONCl	4.50	4.61	...	...	...	...
6.	"	Morpholinyl-	172°	91	C ₁₅ H ₂₁ O ₂ NCl	5.10	4.94	162°	C ₂₁ H ₂₉ O ₉ N ₄	11.60	11.76
7.	"	Piperidyl-	178°	63	C ₁₆ H ₂₄ ONCl	4.85	4.97	...	...	...	...
8.	2-Allyl-4-chloro-	Benzyl-	144°	77	C ₁₇ H ₁₉ ONCl ₂	4.25	4.32	...	...	...	...
9.	"	Morpholinyl-	180°	96	C ₁₄ H ₁₉ O ₂ NCl ₂	4.51	4.60	187°	C ₂₃ H ₃₁ O ₉ N ₂ Cl	1.15	11.28
10.	"	Piperidyl-	175°	90	C ₁₅ H ₂₁ ONCl ₂	4.52	4.63	...	...	...	...
11a*	"	Piperazine	179°	60	C ₂₁ H ₂₉ O ₂ N ₂ Cl ₂	6.15	6.26	...	...	...	...
11b	"	"	208°	...	C ₂₄ H ₃₀ O ₂ N ₂ Cl ₄	5.40	5.39	226°	C ₃₃ H ₄₁ O ₁₀ N ₃ Cl ₄	12.20	12.37
12.	2-Allyl-4-tert-butyl-	Morpholinyl-	171°	98	C ₁₈ H ₂₉ O ₂ NCl	4.42	4.30	204°	C ₂₄ H ₃₀ O ₉ N ₄	10.65	10.81
13.	"	Piperidyl-	203°	92	C ₁₉ H ₂₉ ONCl	4.22	4.33	...	...	...	...
14a*	"	Piperazine-	150°	51	C ₂₃ H ₂₆ O ₂ N ₂	5.80	5.71	...	...	...	...
14b	"	"	222°	...	C ₂₅ H ₂₈ O ₂ N ₂ Cl ₂	4.90	4.97	...	...	...	...

*a-as free Mannich base

b-The hydrochloride of the Mannich base.

E X P E R I M E N T A L

Mannich Base Hydrochlorides.—A mixture of the substituted phenol (0.01M) and the amine (0.013 M) was taken in a round-bottomed flask fitted with a reflux condenser, cooled externally by ice. To this was added calculated amount of a 30% aqueous solution of formaldehyde dropwise under stirring in about 20 minutes, when a thick emulsion was obtained. The flask was removed from the cooling bath and the reaction mixture kept at room temperature for half an hour, after which it was refluxed on the water-bath for another 2 hours, when the Mannich base separated out as an oily layer. To this was added the requisite quantity of sodium chloride (A.R.) and the mixture was refluxed again for about 20 minutes. After cooling, it was extracted with ether and the ether extract was separated and dried over anhydrous magnesium sulphate. Dry HCl gas was passed in the cold ether extract, when the Mannich base hydrochloride separated out as a crystalline mass. It was filtered at the pump, washed with dry ether, then with absolute ethyl alcohol, and finally dried. In majority of the cases the Mannich base hydrochlorides, thus obtained, were pure enough and needed no further crystallisation. However, in certain cases, where the melting point was not sharp, recrystallisation was effected with absolute ethyl alcohol or benzene.

It was observed that the Mannich bases, prepared from piperazine (No. 4a, 11a and 14a in Table I), separated as a crystalline solid instead of an oily layer, after 15 minutes of reflux on the water-bath. These were redissolved in absolute ethyl alcohol and refluxed for another 2 hours after which the hydrochlorides were isolated in the usual way by dissolving them either in ether or benzene and passing dry HCl gas. The Mannich base hydrochlorides were characterised through their picrates.

Picrates.—The Mannich base hydrochloride (II, 0.5 g.) (No. 2, 3, 6 and 9 in Table I) was dissolved in 5 c.c. of hot water. To this was added a slight excess (about 25%) of a saturated aqueous solution of picric acid, when a thick yellow heavy precipitate was obtained. This was boiled gently for sometime and then cooled when the crystalline picrate separated out, which was filtered at the pump, washed with a little alcohol and recrystallised from boiling water.

In certain cases, where the Mannich base hydrochlorides (No. 11 & 12 in Table I) were not soluble in water, these were dissolved in 5 c.c. of rectified spirit and to these 5 c.c. of a cold alcoholic saturated solution of picric acid was added and then warmed on the water-bath for about 5 minutes. On cooling, the picrate separated out which was filtered and recrystallised from alcohol.

The compounds (3, 6, 9 & 13 in Table I) (0.5 g. each) were dissolved in 5 c.c. of water separately and the aqueous solutions allowed to stand at room temperature for 36 hours. The solutions remained transparent throughout. On removing water from each solution, the original compound was recovered in all the cases. The melting points, yields and analyses of the Mannich base hydrochlorides and their picrates are recorded in Table I.

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